

Vanadium. Part IV. Vanadium(IV) and Vanadium(V) Complexes of 3-Hydroxy-1,3-Diphenyltriazene

R. L. Dutta* and Subrata Lahiry

A study of vanadium (IV) and vanadium (V) complexes of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene has been made. The reagent reduces vanadium (V) to vanadium (IV) and then gives rise to an olive-green complex $[VO_2]$. A product of the same composition has also been obtained by interaction of VO_2 and the reagent. The identical nature of these two preparations has been established through their X-ray powder patterns, IR spectra, magnetic moment, and molecular weight determinations. On reacting with pyridine, the compound $[VO_2]$ undergoes oxidation and changes to golden yellow $[VO_2 \cdot T \cdot py]$ which has further been found to yield a greenish black isomer from benzene (TH = a molecule of the ligand).

Since the synthesis of hydroxytriazenes by Bamberger¹ and others², the complexing ability of these ligands has been examined by Elkins and Hunter³. The hydroxytriazenes with the functional group,

were found to produce well-defined, crystalline compounds with representative transition elements³, such as, Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Co(III), Fe(II) and Fe(III). Recently, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene and a few of its derivatives have been investigated as analytical reagents. Satisfactory determinations of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ti(IV), and Ni(II) have been reported⁴.

Sogani and Bhattacharya^{4,5}, in reporting the general reactions of hydroxyphenyltriazene towards different metallic ions, have remarked that vanadium (IV) and vanadium (V) react in dilute acid medium with the reagent to produce a grassy green and a dark green precipitate respectively. Owing to our current interest in the chemistry of coordination complexes of vanadium in different oxidation states, we thought it worthwhile to undertake a detailed study of these reactions. Because of the possible reducing effect of these ligands, it occurred to us that the precipitates, these workers obtained, had vanadium, in all probability, in a lower oxidation state.

When aqueous vanadyl sulphate is added to an ethanolic solution of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene, a green solution is first obtained which on shaking for several minutes changes to brown. The brown-coloured solution soon deposits a highly crystalline, shining, deep olive-green compound. This on analysis corresponds to the formula $[VOT_2]$ (I) (where TH = a molecule of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene). Again, when aqueous ammonium

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan.

1. *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 104; 1897, 30, 2280; 1899, 32, 1677; 1900, 33, 3510.

2. Gebhard and Thompson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 767.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1346.

4. Sogani and Bhattacharya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 81, 1616; 1957, 29, 397.

5. This *Journal*, 1959, 36, 563.

vanadate is added to an ethanolic solution of the reagent and the medium made slightly acid (pH 2-3) with a few drops of dilute (ca. 2*N*) sulphuric acid, a brown solution forms on shaking. The mixture, on being allowed to stand in ice-water, deposits once again a highly crystalline, shining, olive-green product. On analysis, the compound corresponds to the composition, $[\text{VOF}_2]$ (II). We then sought to establish the identical nature of these two preparations. That these are both derivatives of quadrivalent vanadium have been conclusively proved from the following;

(1) Both the samples are paramagnetic; μ_{eff} for (I), 1.77 B.M. and μ_{eff} for (II), 1.74 B.M., indicating one unpaired spin.

(2) That the X-ray diffraction patterns of the compounds are identical will be evident from their 'd' values (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Compound (I): 7.5, 6.3, 5.5, 4.8, 4.6, 3.6, 3.4, 3.4, 3.1, 2.7, 2.5, 1.9

Compound (II): 7.5, 6.3, 5.5, 4.8, 4.6, 3.6, 3.4, 3.1.

FIG. 1. X-ray pattern of compound (I).

FIG. 2. X-ray pattern of compound (II).

(3) The compounds have superimposable IR spectra (Fig. 3, compounds I and II). Both reveal strong vandyl bands at 989 cm^{-1} (979 cm^{-1} shoulder) for (I) and at 989 cm^{-1} (980 cm^{-1} shoulder) for (II).

(4) Both the samples have been found to be monomeric in freezing benzene [MW. of (I) 486 and that of (II), 474].

(5) They have identical decomposition point at 120° .

VANADIUM
% Transmittance.

FIG. 3. IR spectra of compounds (I) and (II).
Continuous lines indicate (I) and broken lines, (II).

These studies therefore reveal that vanadium (V) is reduced to V(IV) by the ligand, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene, in dilute acid medium and then is complexed to furnish $[\text{VOT}_2]$. The analytical results for vanadium, nitrogen, carbon, and hydrogen, as recorded in Table I, are, however, in excellent agreement with the formula (VOT_2) . Therefore, it is to be regarded as a five-co-ordinated entity and that six-co-ordination does not occur through polymerisation is also shown by the monomeric nature of the compound in freezing benzene. This is a non-electrolyte as shown by the poor κ value of the conductance ($1 \Omega^{-1}$) in methanol. A decision between the two possible structures, namely, a square pyramid or a trigonal bipyramid, has to await a full structural investigation. Incidentally, the crystal structure of vanadyl bis-acetylacetonate⁶ has recently been studied and found to possess an approximately square pyramidal structure with vanadium near the centre of gravity of the pyramid.

TABLE I

Compound.	Percentage calculated.				Percentage found.			
	V.	N.	C.	H.	V.	N.	C.	H.
$[\text{VOT}_2]$	10.38	17.10	58.65	4.07	10.40	16.90	58.61	3.61

Since the sixth co-ordination position in the molecule (VOT_2) is vacant, we tried to ascertain the possibility of introducing some other ligands in this position. Such attempts gave some unexpected results. When the olive-green product (VOT_2) is treated with a little pyridine, a green solution is formed which, when warmed on a water bath, changes to brown. From this brown-coloured solution, bright golden yellow to yellow needles are obtained on cooling. The compound corresponds to the composition $(\text{VO}_2\text{T.py})$. This is diamagnetic, indicative of quinquevalency for vanadium in the compound. This shows a conductance value of $6 \Omega^{-1}$ in methanol. The low value of conductance rules out the possibility of such formula, e.g., $\text{pyH}[\text{VO}_2(\text{OH})\text{T}]$. These observations suggest that as the pyridine molecule advances towards the sixth co-ordination position, surroundings become basic, facilitating oxidation. During the oxidative reactions, one of the two ligands is knocked off the co-ordination sphere. Somewhat similar observation was also made with respect to oxo-hydroxo-bis-quinquinaldinato-vanadium (V), reported earlier. This compound, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, on heating with pyridine also broke down and furnished crystals of pyridine-dioxo-monquinquinaldinato-vanadium (V), $(\text{VO}_2\text{Q.py})$. Oxo-bis-quinquinaldinato-vanadium (IV), (VOQ_2) , however, readily furnished insoluble products of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{X})\text{Q}_2]$ (where, X = py, <-pic, etc.). It was also observed that the green-coloured pyridine solution of (VOT_2) changed to yellow on oxidation with a stream of air.

The compound $(\text{VO}_2\text{T.py})$ can be represented either as a five-co-ordinated monomer or a six-co-ordinated dimer:

In freezing benzene, monomeric value for the molecular weight was only obtained.

TABLE II

Oryoscopic determination of molecular weight.
Benzene (W)=21.82g.

Compound.	Wt. of the substance (w).	ΔT .	Mol. wt. (M).	
			Found	Calc.
1. $[\text{VO}_2](\text{I})$	0.04146 g.	0.020°	486.0	491
2. $[\text{VO}_2](\text{II})$	0.08485	0.042°	474.0	"
3. $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py}]$	0.04090	0.026°	399.0	374
4. $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.}\leftarrow\text{pic.}]$	0.04140	0.025°	388.6	388

Calculated from the relation: $M = Kw/\Delta T \times W$, where K is 5120.

It is of further interest to mention here that the benzene solution of the bright golden yellow compound, $(\text{VO}_2\text{T.py})$, changes on standing from yellow to green. The molecular weight, found, is presumably that of this green species, rather than that of the original golden yellow variety. The golden yellow compound on repeated treatment with pure benzene left an intense green-black product, which also gave correct analytical figures for a compound with empirical composition, $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py}]$.

TABLE III

Compound.	Percentage calculated.				Percentage found (green).			
	V.	N.	C.	H.	V.	N.	C.	H.
1. $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py}]$	13.63	14.97	54.54	4.01				
2. $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_6]$	11.28	12.39	61.06	4.64				
3. $(\text{VO}_2\text{T} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_6)$	13.67	11.26	57.91	4.29	13.68	15.10	55.06	4.40
4. $[\text{VO}_2\text{T}]$	17.28	14.23	48.81	3.39				

The analytical figures of the green variety, being very close to those of the yellow form, rule out any possibility of the formation of an octahedral complex with benzene being π -bonded in the complex zone. This, too, is diamagnetic. The golden yellow compound $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py}]$ suffers practically no loss at 100° for at least six hours though the colour changes from bright yellow to yellowish green. After heating for about 24 hours, a greenish black powder is, however, obtained which gives analyses corresponding approximately to $[\text{VO}_2\text{T}]$. The green variety from benzene is also found to be diamagnetic. The diamagnetic susceptibilities of the yellow and green varieties along with values of mass susceptibilities, diamagnetic corrections, and effective moments of other compounds are recorded in Table IV.

With a monomeric form the compound $[\text{VO}_2\text{T.py}]$ can have two structural forms, a square pyramid or a trigonal bipyramid. It is also quite possible that they have the same structural form, but differ in the relative disposition of the co-ordinated groups. The IR spectra of these two isomeric varieties indicate lesser number of bands in the green form. This might be taken to indicate the symmetrical 'trans' structure for the green isomer. We contemplate to undertake a structural investigation of these two isomers.

TABLE IV

Magnetic measurements.

Temp. = 32°.

Compound.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	Diamagnetic correction ($\times 10^6$).	μ_{eff} (B.M.).
1. [VO ₂ T ₂] (I)	2.085	259*	1.77
Do (II)	1.974	259	1.74
2. [VO ₂ T ₂ .py] (A) (yellow)	-0.165	..	Diamagnetic
Do (B) (green)	-0.102	..	..
3. [VO ₂ T ₂ . α -pic.]	-0.138	..	..
4. [VO ₂ T ₂ .anil.]	-0.105	..	..

The olive-green product, (VOT₂) also reacts similarly with α -picoline and aniline to furnish crystalline golden yellow products of the composition [VO₂T₂.X] (where X = α -picoline or aniline). These are also diamagnetic and monomeric in freezing benzene. Their benzene solutions also exhibit a green colour on standing. The general scheme of reactions studied is shown in Chart I.

CHART I

[TH=3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene]

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene, was prepared according to the procedure adopted by Sogani and Bhattacharya⁴ and was recrystallised twice from rectified spirit.

Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazeno-vanadium (IV)

(I). 3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazeno (0.6 g.), dissolved in warm ethanol (60 ml), was treated with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g. in 10 ml). The green solution on stirring changed to brown and on keeping deposited shining olive-green crystals. After cooling for sometime in an ice bath, the crystals were filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried *in vacuo* over CaCl_2 . {Found: C, 58.61; H, 3.61; N, 16.9; V, 10.4. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires C, 58.65; H, 4.07; N, 17.1; V, 10.38%}.

(II). The ethanolic solution of the reagent (1.2 g. in 100 ml ethanol) was treated with an aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.2g. in 10ml) and the pH adjusted to 2-3 with a few drops of dilute (*ca.* 2N) H_2SO_4 . The solution on keeping furnished a crop of shining olive-green crystals. {Found: N, 17.1; V, 10.3. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2]$ requires N, 17.1; V, 10.38%}.

These are readily soluble in benzene or acetone, yielding a green solution but sparingly so in methanol.

Pyridine-diozo-mono-3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazeno-vanadium(V)

A. *Golden Yellow Variety*.—Oxo-bis-3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazeno-vanadium (IV) (prepared from 0.5 g. VOSO_4 and 1.2 g. reagent, as described above) was treated with freshly distilled pyridine (5 ml). A deep green solution, first formed, changed to dark brown-yellow on warming. This was cooled in ice for an hour, when bright golden yellow needles separated. These were filtered, washed with ice-cold ethanol, and dried over CaCl_2 . {Found: C, 54.9; H, 3.12; N, 15.05; V, 13.35. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires C, 54.54; H, 4.01; N, 14.97; V, 13.63%}.

The compound is soluble in ethanol with a golden yellow colour, whereas in benzene and acetone it first produces a golden yellow colour which on standing changes to green.

The same golden yellow compound was also obtained by addition of aqueous vanadyl sulphate to an ethanol-pyridine solution of the reagent, warming, and then cooling.

B. *Green-black Variety*.—The golden yellow compound, as described above, was dissolved in a large volume of pure benzene. The original yellow colour changed to green after several minutes. The green solution was stored in a stoppered vessel for a couple of hours, filtered, and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. {Found: C, 55.06; H, 4.49; N, 15.10; V, 13.68. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$ requires C, 54.54; H, 4.01; N, 14.97; V, 13.63%}.

 α -Picoline-diozo-mono-3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazeno-vanadium (V)

The golden yellow compound was obtained in the same way as for the corresponding pyridine complex, using α -picoline instead of pyridine. {Found: N, 14.5; V, 12.9. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O})(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})]$ requires N, 14.4; V, 13.1%}. The compound dissolves readily in ethanol producing a yellow colour, whereas in benzene or acetone a green colour is obtained.

Aniline-dioxo-mono-3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene-ranadium (V)

The golden yellow compound was prepared similarly as for the corresponding pyridine compound, using aniline instead of pyridine. {Found: N, 14.4; V, 12.8. $[\text{VO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{N}_3\text{O}) \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH}_2)]$ requires N, 14.4; V, 13.1%}.

The authors thank Dr. K. Banerjee, Director of this Institute, for providing laboratory facilities, Dr. D. K. Banerjee of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, and Mrs. C. Dutta of this Institute, for the analyses of carbon and hydrogen, and Dr. Ranjit Sen for the X-ray studies. They also thank Dr. J. Xavier for kindly running the infrared spectrograms while at the University of Maryland, U. S. A.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA-32.

Received July 9, 1962.